

1 The Food Contact Chemicals Health **Impact Effect**
2 Matrix (FCChelix): Protocol for a systematic evidence
3 map

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25 Abstract

26 *Background:* Food contact chemicals (FCCs) are known to migrate from food packaging
27 and other food contact articles into food. This leads to human exposure to FCCs, and
28 some FCCs have been linked to human health effects such as chronic and non-
29 communicable diseases. However, a systematic overview of the health [effects/impacts](#)
30 of FCCs is missing.

31 *Objectives:* The objective of this study is to systematically map the relations between
32 exposure to FCCs and human health effects within the Population, Exposure,
33 Comparator, Outcomes, and Study Design (PECOS) framework.

34 *Search strategy and eligibility criteria:* We will search PubMed for combinations of
35 search terms related to the identity of the chemical and the epidemiological study
36 design. The references will be screened at title and abstract level, followed by full-text
37 level. Eligible references will be included according to predefined criteria, further
38 [specifying](#) the elements of the applied PECOS framework.

39 *Data extraction and coding:* Information on human exposure to FCCs will be collected
40 and linked to human health effects according to previously defined data categories and
41 standardized terms. The human health effects will be classified based on the Six
42 Clusters of Disease (SCOD) framework.

43 *Synthesis and visualization:* Results will be published in a narrative summary and data
44 will be made available in a freely accessible interactive dashboard, [the Food Contact](#)
45 [Chemicals Health Effect Matrix \(FCChelix\)](#).

46 Introduction

47 Rationale

48 Humans are exposed to many synthetic chemicals from various sources, and exposure
49 to some of these chemicals has been linked to the rise of non-communicable diseases
50 (Martínez-Ibarra et al., 2021; Symeonides et al., 2024). Food packaging and other food
51 contact articles (FCAs) contribute to this exposure via oral uptake because food contact
52 chemicals (FCCs) migrate from food contact materials (FCMs) into foodstuffs (Muncke
53 et al., 2020).

54 Regulating FCMs and managing the risks associated with chemical migration from
55 FCMs is challenging. Firstly, hundreds of FCCs with hazard properties of concern are
56 used in FCMs (Zimmermann et al., 2022) and legislation often lags far behind
57 toxicological research (Muncke et al., 2017). Secondly, many FCCs do not have
58 sufficient migration, hazard, and exposure data to assess their risks, and this is even
59 more pronounced for non-intentionally added substances (NIAS), such as degradation
60 products, contaminants, impurities, and by-products (Nerin et al., 2013; Nerín et al.,
61 2022).

62 To understand which FCCs are used in the manufacture of FCMs, we ~~have previously~~
63 compiled the Food Contact Chemicals Database (FCCdb), listing publicly available
64 evidence on >12,000 intentionally used FCCs (Groh et al., 2021). However, during FCM
65 manufacturing, many intentionally used FCCs are chemically transformed, leading to
66 the generation of expected reaction products as well as NIAS. To better understand
67 which chemicals are present in FCMs, we also published a systematic evidence map on
68 FCCs that have been analyzed in migrates and/or extracts of FCMs (Geueke et al.,
69 2023). The resulting Database on Migrating and Extractable Food Contact Chemicals
70 (FCCmigex) is available as an interactive dashboard (Food Packaging Forum, 2025).
71 FCCmigex currently contains information on 5,295 FCCs from 1,500 references.
72 Together, the FCCdb and FCCmigex databases include >15,000 FCCs, but the overlap
73 between them is small, as only 28% of the FCCs detected in migrates and/or extracts
74 are also part of the FCCdb. The remaining 72% of the chemicals in the FCCmigex

75 database may be present as NIAS or ~~they~~ may have been used intentionally without
76 being listed in the sources included in the FCCdb. Migration from FCMs indicates a high
77 probability of human exposure, albeit with some uncertainty. To understand the extent
78 of human exposure to FCCs, we systematically compiled the Database on Food
79 Contact Chemicals Monitored in Humans (FCChumon) (Food Packaging Forum, 2024;
80 Geueke, Parkinson, et al., 2024). In total, 25% of the known FCCs have been detected in
81 humans. While not dismissing exposure sources other than FCMs, these data
82 nonetheless help to link exposure from FCMs to the presence of FCCs in humans, and
83 they also support the identification of knowledge gaps.

84 The ~~FCCdb, FCCmigex, and FCChumon~~ ~~three~~ databases ~~described above~~ provide
85 systematically compiled information on the use of FCCs in the manufacture of FCMs as
86 well as their presence in migrates and/or extracts of FCMs and in human samples.

87 However, ~~comprehensive data on human health effects exist for only a small fraction of~~
88 ~~these chemicals. there is no comprehensive overview linking FCC exposures to human~~
89 ~~health effects. T~~For example, the Plastic Health Map summarizes human health effects
90 of selected plastic-associated chemicals and particles, including polymers,
91 plasticizers, flame retardants, bisphenols, and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
92 (PFAS) (Minderoo Foundation, 2023; Seewoo et al., 2023). Further systematic evidence
93 maps and scoping reviews associating chemical exposure and human health ~~outcomes~~
94 have been published, such as on bisphenol A (Zhu et al., 2024), PFAS (Pelch et al., 2022;
95 Radke et al., 2022; Ricolfi et al., 2024; Shirke et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2023),
96 polyethylene terephthalate (PET) oligomers (Schreier et al., 2023), and persistent
97 organic pollutants (Carlson et al., 2023; Payne-Sturges et al., 2023; Yost et al., 2021). A
98 recent umbrella review focused on selected plastic-related exposures to chemicals
99 across a broad range of groups and identified at least one adverse health outcome for
100 each group (Symeonides et al., 2024). Based on a gap analysis, the authors ~~of the~~
101 ~~umbrella review~~ prioritized micro- and nanoplastics, bisphenol analogues, non-
102 phthalate plasticizers, and alternative flame retardants as key priority areas for further
103 research. ~~For other chemical groups broadly used in FCMs, such as synthetic phenolic~~
104 ~~antioxidants, studies on human health effects are scarce~~ (Hao et al., 2023).

105 Recent regulatory actions addressed the health risks of certain chemical groups by
106 establishing legally enforceable limits on, e.g., PFAS in food packaging waste (EU
107 2025/40) and bisphenols in FCMs (EU 2024/3190).

108 However, mMany current regulatory approaches to chemical risk assessment for FCCs
109 primarily emphasize evaluating the genotoxicity of chemicals used as starting
110 substances in the production of FCMs. This neglects the presence of NIAS in FCMs and
111 other toxicity toxicological endpoints that are also of high concern. One notable
112 development is the recent regulatory amendment on plastic FCMs (EU 2025/351) that
113 introduced more details on the required risk assessment of NIAS in the EU.

114 In 2023, we grouped chronic health outcomes that are highly prevalent in the human
115 population were grouped into Six Clusters of Disease (SCOD), including cancers,
116 cardiovascular diseases, reproductive disorders, brain-related disorders,
117 immunological disorders, and metabolic diseases (Figure 1) (Muncke et al., 2023). T. We
118 further recommended the better understand the impact of FCCs on human health, the
119 development of high-throughput screening assays for endpoints related to these
120 disease clusters was recommended. Such high-throughput methods would allow which
121 allow assessing toxicological endpoints related to these clusters and testing of all
122 migrating FCCs. However, To support this approach, it is also essential to understand
123 the epidemiologic data linking exposure to FCCs to diseases categorized under the
124 SCOD framework. This knowledge can support the development of screening assays.

125
126 Figure 1. The Six Clusters of Disease (SCOD) concept comprises highly-prevalent, non-
127 communicable diseases that are of increasing concern and associated with hazardous
128 chemical exposures (according to (Muncke et al., 2023)).

129 Objectives

130 ~~We will~~Our aim is to systematically map the literature examining the established links
131 between exposure to known FCCs and adverse human health outcomes. ~~We will~~
132 ~~include human studies that investigate the relationship between exposure to FCCs and~~
133 ~~health effects.~~ We will particularly focus on FCCs that have been detected in FCMs and
134 in human samples (Geueke et al., 2023; Geueke, Parkinson, et al., 2024). Health
135 outcomes will be assigned to the SCOD (Figure 1) [22]. The international classification
136 of diseases (11th revision, ICD-11; (World Health Organisation, 2022)) will be used as
137 basis for these assignments.

138 ~~The resulting systematic evidence map will summarize available data and identify~~
139 ~~knowledge gaps.~~ The systematic evidence map will allow the identification of FCCs (i)
140 that are associated with human health effects and (ii) for which more data on exposure
141 and/or health effects are needed. Additionally, it ~~will~~aims to provide information for
142 more specific research questions that are, for example, related to certain chemicals or
143 chemical groups, types of FCMs, specific health outcomes, or vulnerable populations.
144 The data will be presented in an interactive and openly accessible dashboard, the Food
145 Contact Chemicals Health Effect Matrix (FCChelix), and key findings will be
146 summarized in a peer-reviewed article.

147 Methods

148 This protocol was drafted following the updated 2015 PRISMA-P guidelines (Preferred
149 Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols; Annex 3) (Moher et
150 al., 2015; Page et al., 2021) and giving due consideration to the recommendations for
151 the Conduct of Systematic Reviews in Toxicology and Environmental Health Research
152 (COSTER) (Whaley et al., 2020).

153 Research question

154 The PECOS (Population, Exposure, Comparator, Outcome, Study Design) framework will
155 be applied to answer the research question: Which FCCs are associated with non-
156 communicable chronic diseases in humans? (Table 1).

157 Table 1. Elements of the research question following the PECOS framework.

Element of PECOS framework	Description
Population	Any human
Exposure	To FCCs or metabolites of FCCs
Comparator	Control groups or any other comparator
Outcome	Human health effects related to the Six Clusters of Disease (SCOD)
Study design	Epidemiological studies

158 Eligibility criteria

159 Inclusion and exclusion criteria are defined to facilitate decisions on the eligibility of a
 160 reference during literature screening (Table 2). They are structured according to the
 161 elements of the PECOS framework. Studies meeting one or more exclusion criteria will
 162 be excluded. Eligible studies contain primary data, have been peer-reviewed, and are
 163 published in English. There will be no general restriction regarding the publication date.

164 The systematic evidence map will consider studies on any human *population* globally,
 165 without restrictions on age, sex, life stage, and pre-existing health conditions. Studies
 166 on animals and human cell lines will be excluded. Data from a control group are
 167 included in the study, serving as comparator.

168 Studies are required to report the detection of FCCs in human samples (indicating
 169 exposure) and link them to human health effects. We will only consider epidemiological
 170 studies on FCCs that have been previously detected in migrates and/or extracts of FCMs
 171 (Food Packaging Forum, 2025). For some FCCs, specific metabolites are known and
 172 routinely assessed (e.g., phthalates). If such metabolites have been detected in
 173 humans, the exposure element of the framework is fulfilled.

174 Only measurements of human health effects will be included. The health *outcomes* can
 175 be classified into at least one of these six disease clusters (i.e., SCOD): cancers,
 176 cardiovascular diseases, reproductive disorders, brain-related disorders,
 177 immunological disorders, and metabolic diseases (Figure 1). Studies reporting the
 178 diagnoses of a disease will be included (e.g., diabetes), as well as studies on
 179 physiological and/or biochemical measurement that are associated with changes in

180 relevant organ systems (e.g., ovaries, brain). A longitudinal or cross-sectional study
 181 design is required; case reports will be excluded.

182 Table 2. Elements of the PECOS framework and eligibility criteria to be applied during literature
 183 screening. Studies that meet any exclusion criteria will not be considered eligible.

Element of PECOS framework	Inclusion	Exclusion
Population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any human, without restriction based on age, sex, life stage, and preexisting health conditions, including the developing fetus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyzed sample originates from an animal, plant, fungi, and bacteria, is an environmental sample, or is not defined Sample is a human cell line
Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyzed sample originates from a human specimen (e.g., blood, urine, breast milk) AND at least one analyte is an FCC that has previously been detected in extracts/migrates of FCMs (i.e., the chemical is listed in the FCCmigex database) or a specific metabolite of such an FCC (i.e., the parent compound is specifically transformed into the analyte) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FCC or its specific metabolite is listed in the FCCdb, but has never been detected in migrates or extracts of FCMs according to the FCCmigex database Modelling of chemical exposure Dermal exposure, such as patch and skin-prick tests
Comparator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All studies including a control group or any other comparator 	
Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any health outcome that can be related to the Six Clusters of Disease (SCOD) Direct reporting of a disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Missing/incomplete assessment of health outcome Health outcome cannot be aligned with SCOD Modelling of health outcomes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measurement of physiological and/or biochemical changes associated with the SCOD 	
Study design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epidemiological studies including longitudinal or cross-sectional study designs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case study/report • Descriptive studies

184 Stakeholder engagement

185 During the development of this protocol, we had regular meetings with the core team,
186 and the scientific advisory group (SAG) of the Food Contact Chemicals and human
187 Health (FCCH) project (Food Packaging Forum). The members of these two groups have
188 expertise in the fields of FCMs and FCCs, toxicology, epidemiology, chemical
189 databases, and systematic evidence mapping. Between August 2024 and January 2025,
190 we had monthly meetings with the core team. The core team has been deeply involved
191 in protocol development, literature screening and data extraction of previous
192 systematic evidence maps related to the FCCH project (i.e., FCCmigex and FCChumon)
193 (Geueke et al., 2023; Geueke, Parkinson, et al., 2024). Therefore, its members have a
194 detailed understanding of the underlying data and processes and provided valuable
195 input throughout the development of this protocol. All core team members are co-
196 authors of this protocol. Advice was also given by Louise Goodes from Minderoo
197 Foundation, who is the first author of the protocol of the Plastic Health Map (Goodes et
198 al., 2022). Additionally, the SAG of the FCCH project was consulted twice during
199 protocol development and asked for input during online meetings.

200 Information sources

201 We investigated the suitability of the databases PubMed, Medline (Ovid), Embiology®,
202 SciFinder®, and ScienceDirect® for this project. PubMed offers the most advantages in
203 terms of coverage of the literature, the possibility to run automated searches, and the
204 availability of search and filter options. Furthermore, PubMed is freely available and
205 focuses on medical/health related topics, and accessibility. As the use of only one
206 database also simplifies the workflow, data management and future updates for

207 [hundreds to thousands of individual FCCs](#), PubMed will be used for all literature
208 searches.

209 Search strategy

210 The ideal search strategy ~~will identify~~ [identifies](#) as many relevant published studies on
211 FCCs and human health outcomes as reasonably feasible. However, the available
212 evidence for individual chemicals and chemical groups varies strongly. Therefore, we
213 developed a modular search strategy including study-related search terms, defined
214 filter options, and chemical-related search terms that will allow us to customize the
215 literature searches within given boundaries ([Figure 2](#)~~Figure 2~~). [This strategy is markedly](#)
216 [different and less complex than the searches employed by the Plastic Health Map](#)
217 [\(Seewoo et al., 2023\)](#).

218
219 Figure 2. Modular search strategy. Study-related search terms aim at identifying epidemiological
220 studies. Filter settings allow the selection of, e.g., the studied species (i.e., humans), [publication](#)
221 [data and type and](#) language, ~~and publication date~~. Chemical-related search terms include
222 common chemical names, synonyms and identifiers.

223 Scoping searches

224 We applied different strategies to identify search terms related to the study design of
225 epidemiological research. First, we brainstormed study-related search terms within the
226 core team and refined this list by running iterative searches. Then, we analyzed the word
227 frequencies of the reference titles included in the Plastic Health Map, as this
228 [benchmark](#) database addressed a similar research question regarding plastic-
229 associated chemicals in general (no specific focus on FCCs) (Seewoo et al., 2023).

230 [Word frequency](#) analysis was supported by using the Voyant tools (Sinclar et al., 2024).

231 Iterative testing of these preliminary terms resulted in a short and a long list of study-
232 related search terms (Table S1). We also applied different filter settings for the studied
233 species (i.e., human) and publication types. By combining the different study-related
234 search terms and filters, we obtained four search options and tested them for different

235 FCCs and groups of FCCs. ~~This strategy is markedly different and less complex than the~~
236 ~~searches employed by the Plastic Health Map (Seewoo et al., 2023).~~

237 A comparison of the results of our scoping searches for bisphenols, phthalates, and
238 per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) with the benchmark references included in
239 the Plastic Health Map illustrated that our search options successfully captured 80-
240 97% of the ~~m.se benchmark references~~ (see Supplementary information, Figure S1).
241 Refining of the chemical related-search terms improved the overlap coverage of a test
242 search for PFAS from initially 50 to 92% (Figure S2). Importantly, in a preliminary
243 screening of the reference list for bisphenols, we identified even more eligible
244 references that have not been included in the Plastic Health Map (see Supplementary
245 information, section 4). More detailed analyses showed that most of the studies missed
246 by the scoping searches are included in PubMed but were not found because the study-
247 related search terms covered the expected literature very well, as most of the missing
248 references were not found because the chemical names were are not mentioned in the
249 titles, abstracts or keywords (Figure S3). This limitation may be overcome by using
250 additional chemical synonyms. ~~In a preliminary screening of the reference list for~~
251 ~~bisphenols, we identified even more eligible references that have not been included in~~
252 ~~the Plastic Health Map (see Supplementary information, section 4).~~ Based on the
253 results of these scoping searches, we considered our general search strategy to be
254 appropriate in terms of sensitivity and specificity.

255 Implementing the literature searches

256 Automated literature searches will be conducted in PubMed using the Entrez
257 Programming Utilities API. This approach will enable the systematic retrieval of records
258 for each FCC.

259 We will use the short list of study-related search terms as default setting, since it
260 balances sensitivity (i.e., identifying the benchmark references) and specificity (i.e.,
261 keeping the screening effort low) (search option 1, Table S1; Table 3).

262 In accordance with the eligibility criteria, the language filter for English and the
263 publication type “journal article” will be selected, and the publication types “review”
264 and “case report” will be excluded. The species filter for “humans” will be selected. No

265 date limit will be set. Only for FCCs that are already included in the Plastic Health Map,
 266 we will search for references that were published after January 31, 2022 (i.e., the last
 267 update of the Plastic Health Map). This will prevent duplication of work, as the Plastic
 268 Health Map addressed a similar research question, and it is supported by the results of
 269 our scoping exercise (see Supplementary Information).

270 ~~Most FCCs have different chemical synonyms and can be linked to chemical identifiers~~
 271 ~~such as CAS RN, InCHI and SMILES (Geueke & Parkinson, 2024; Groh et al., 2022):~~

272 ~~However,~~ searching the scientific literature for individual chemicals is often
 273 challenging as chemical names can have many different spellings and are often only
 274 mentioned in the full text, tables and/or figures, which makes them undetectable in
 275 most literature searches. Additionally, chemical identifiers such as CAS RN, InCHI and
 276 SMILES are rarely used in epidemiological studies. To address this and cover the
 277 chemical space more broadly, we will perform individual searches for each FCC and
 278 include names used in the FCC databases, CompTox, and CAS Common Chemistry, as
 279 well as IUPAC synonyms and CAS RNs (Geueke & Parkinson, 2024; Groh et al., 2022).
 280 Chemical synonyms and identifiers will be connected by the operator OR, as illustrated
 281 in Table 3 the scoping searches (Figure S2). We will also search for groups of FCCs that
 282 have been assigned on the basis of similar functional or structural properties, because
 283 the group names may be mentioned in titles, abstracts, or keywords while individual
 284 chemical names may not. Work on the grouping of FCCs is currently ongoing at the
 285 Food Packaging Forum and will be applicable for this project.

286 Table 3. Search terms and filters to query for 1. an individual chemical (here: melamine) and 2. a
 287 chemical group (here: PFAS).

Study-related	Filters	Chemical-related (examples)
(NHANES OR HBM4EU OR CHMS OR KONEHS OR odds OR cross-sectional OR case-control OR cohort OR incidence OR prevalence OR epidemiol* OR associat*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Language: English ● Publication type: "journal article" 	(melamine OR 108-78-1 OR "2,4,6- triamino-s-triazine") (PFAS OR perfluor* OR polyfluor*)

<p><u>OR prospective OR longitudinal OR urin*)</u></p>	<p><u>NOT</u> <u>”review”</u> <u>NOT “case report”</u> <u>• Species:</u> <u>human</u></p>	
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288

289 ~~We will use search option 1 (Table S1), as it balances sensitivity (i.e., identifying the~~
 290 ~~benchmark references) and specificity (i.e., keeping the screening effort low). This~~
 291 ~~means, we will apply the short list of study-related search terms (NHANES OR HBM4EU~~
 292 ~~OR GHMS OR KONEHS OR odds OR cross-sectional OR case-control OR cohort OR~~
 293 ~~incidence OR prevalence OR epidemiot* OR associat* OR prospective OR longitudinal~~
 294 ~~OR urin*) and the species filter for humans as the default search settings and combine~~
 295 ~~them with the chemical-related search terms.~~

296 ~~The scoping searches showed that the available evidence for individual chemicals and~~
 297 ~~chemical groups varies strongly. The potential for certain chemical names to yield~~
 298 ~~unspecific results (e.g., “phenol”), and the possibility of missing studies due to the~~
 299 ~~omission of commonly used chemical synonyms may reduce the specificity and~~
 300 ~~sensitivity of the search results, respectively. These limitations will be acknowledged in~~
 301 ~~the interpretation of the findings and addressed, if possible, through iterative refinement~~
 302 ~~of search terms. For example, if the literature search for an FCC (group) of particular~~
 303 ~~interest will not result in any eligible references, we will consider conducting additional~~
 304 ~~broader literature searches to make sure that we did not miss relevant information. For~~
 305 ~~chemicals where the search results indicate many unspecific hits, searching only the~~
 306 ~~titles and abstracts for the chemical names may reduce the number of irrelevant~~
 307 ~~studies.~~

308 Considerations on prioritizing FCCs

309 Scoping searches revealed substantial variability for individual chemicals and chemical
 310 groups, ranging from zero to tens of thousands of studies found. This is mainly

311 attributed to the differences in the volume of existing research between chemicals. To
312 effectively address our research question and optimize the use of available resources,
313 we will

- 314 • focus on FCCs and groups of FCCs of particular interest (e.g., high evidence for
315 presence in FCMs, high level of concern),
- 316 • exclude FCCs for which there is widely recognized evidence linking chemical
317 exposure to human health effects (e.g., certain heavy metals and volatile organic
318 compounds, and pharmaceuticals found to present in FCMs), and
- 319 • exclude FCCs that are inorganic compounds, endogenous metabolites and/or
320 naturally occurring constituents of food.

321 By applying this prioritization strategy, we aim to focus on the most relevant FCCs that
322 are attributed to FCMs, while avoiding duplication of existing research.

323 If the literature search for an FCC (group) of particular interest (e.g., high evidence for
324 presence in FCMs, high level of concern) will not result in any eligible references, we will
325 deselect the species filter for humans and/or use the long list of study-related search
326 terms to cover the literature more broadly (options 2-4, Table S1). As we will carry out
327 searches for individual chemicals, we will document which studies were found for
328 which FCC and label the studies accordingly before duplicate removal. This will allow
329 us to maintain the link between chemicals and studies during screening and data
330 extraction.

331 During PubMed searches, the language filter for English will be applied and no date limit
332 will be set. Only for FCCs that are already included in the Plastic Health Map, we will
333 search for references that were published after January 31, 2022 (i.e., the last update of
334 the Plastic Health Map). This will prevent duplication of work, as the Plastic Health Map
335 addressed a similar research question, and it is supported by the results of our scoping
336 exercise (see Supplementary Information). Especially for heavy metals (e.g., lead) and
337 some volatile organic compounds (e.g., benzene), international organizations and
338 government agencies have published high-level, widely recognized reports linking
339 chemical exposure to human health effects (Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease
340 Registry, 2020, 2024; EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain, 2010; World

341 Health Organization International Agency for Research on Cancer, 2006, 2018).~~As these~~
342 ~~sources broadly cover the epidemiological literature, we will exclude chemicals covered~~
343 ~~by such recognized reports from the literature searches but refer to these summary~~
344 ~~reports instead.~~

345 Screening process

346 Duplicates within the search results will be identified based on their PubMed ID and
347 removed by using Excel ~~and/or Python~~, optionally followed by using the deduplication
348 function in SWIFT-Active Screener (Howard et al., 2020). For each reference, we will
349 maintain the links to the chemicals for which the respective studies have been found
350 because this information will facilitate data extraction.

351 All studies retrieved from the literature searches will be first screened in SWIFT-Active
352 Screener at title-and-abstract level, followed by full-text screening. The screening of the
353 titles and abstracts will be actively supported by SWIFT-Active Screener, which
354 iteratively prioritizes all references for manual screening. A 95% recall level will be set,
355 which defines the proportion of eligible studies to be included based on the prediction.
356 Studies that clearly do not meet all the inclusion criteria (Table 2) will be excluded
357 during either the title-and-abstract or the full-text screening. Initially, we will perform a
358 consistency check on 10% of the references at the title-and-abstract level to refine the
359 eligibility criteria, where two experts will screen in parallel. Disagreements will be
360 recorded, inter-rater reliability scores will be determined, and conflicts will be resolved.
361 ~~We will also develop~~Any learnings at this early screening stage will be included in a
362 guidance document~~for the screening team~~. If the IRR score exceeds 0.7 at this stage,
363 indicating acceptable agreement according to (Hanegraaf et al., 2024), the remaining
364 titles and abstracts will be screened independently by one reviewer only. If the IRR is
365 below 0.7, we will continue with parallel screening for the next 10% of studies and then
366 re-evaluate the IRR score. This process will repeat until the IRR surpasses the threshold
367 of 0.7, at which point single screening will start, or the recall level predicted by SWIFT-
368 Active Screener is reached and screening can be stopped.~~The screening of the~~
369 ~~remaining titles and abstracts will be actively supported by SWIFT-Active Screener,~~
370 ~~which iteratively prioritizes all references for further manual screening. The references~~

371 included in the consistency check will be used as a training set to build the prioritization
 372 model. A 95% recall level will be set, which defines the proportion of eligible studies to
 373 be included based on the prediction. All included references included after title and
 374 abstract screening will then be screened at full-text level and for consistency, t.
 375 For further consistency, ten percent of the se references will be screened independently
 376 and in parallel by two team members at both screening levels. Any discrepancies will be
 377 resolved by bilateral discussions, with the option to ask a third team member for their
 378 opinion. The IRR score will be tracked, and we will follow the same process as described
 379 above for title and abstract screening. A PRISMA flow diagram will be generated that
 380 provides an overview of the studies found in the literature searches, how many of them
 381 were included/excluded at the two different screening levels, and the reasons for
 382 exclusion at full text level (Figure 3Figure 3).

383

384 Figure 3. Example workflow based on the PRISMA flow diagram. Individual literature searches
 385 will be run for each FCC. ¹Clearly irrelevant studies will be excluded during title and abstract
 386 screening. ²Reasons for exclusion during full text screening may be: full text not accessible, no
 387 primary data presented, exclusion criteria fulfilled.

388 Data extraction

389 Data will be extracted from all studies included after the full-text screening. The in-
390 house software tool SciExtract will be used to compile the data based on pre-coded
391 options and free text. SciExtract allows us to compile the data in a highly structured
392 way, and it supports organizing and managing the workflow, tracking changes, and
393 storing the studies' pdfs and extracted data. We will include relevant publication
394 details, information on the population, chemical exposure, health outcome(s) and
395 study design (Table 4~~Table 3~~, SI_draft data extraction code book).

396 After setting up data extraction templates in SciExtract, we will test the process with a
397 defined set of references. At least two team members will independently extract ~~10% of~~
398 ~~the data from a subset of studies independently~~ and compare the results. Potential
399 conflicts will be discussed and either resolved directly, or input from an additional team
400 member will be called in. After this testing process, data extraction templates may be
401 revised, and an additional guidance document will be prepared to facilitate consistent
402 data extraction. The data from the remaining references will be extracted by one team
403 member and the option to call for an additional opinion will be implemented in the task
404 management process. If necessary, the guidance document will be refined during the
405 data extraction process and all team members will be regularly informed about
406 potential edits. It will be ensured that updates will not conflict with existing data (e.g.,
407 the addition of response options to a predefined selection is often possible). The option
408 to exclude references during data extraction will be permitted to revise decisions
409 regarding a study's eligibility made during the full-text screening process. Such
410 decisions will always require ~~the~~ review by and agreement from a second team
411 member.

412 Table ~~43~~. Data that will be reported based on pre-coded options.

Data category	Data captured
Bibliographic information	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Author(s)• Title• Year of publication• Journal

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • URL • Volume • Issue • Pages • DOI • Abstract
Information on studied population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population type • Number of participants • Biological sex • Ethnicity • Socio-economic status • Age at which exposure was measured • Age at which health outcome was measured • Country of investigated population • Special risk population and comparator group
Chemical information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical name(s) • CAS RN • Optional: Chemical group • Multiple exposures • Detection frequencies
Health outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predefined categories based on the SCOD* (cancer, cardiovascular diseases, reproductive disorders, brain-related disorders, immunological disorders, metabolic diseases)
Study design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predefined categories, such as cross-sectional and longitudinal studies

413 *If an FCC is linked to more than one disease cluster, several database entries will be generated
414 reflecting these multiple associations.

415 The extracted information a given chemical in an epidemiological study. Therefore, the
416 chemical names will be matched to CAS RNs in a post-processing step, following a
417 previously described process (Geueke et al., 2023). A critical appraisal of the studies
418 and extracted data will not be included, which is in line with the methodology of a
419 systematic evidence mapping.

420 Data analysis and presentation

421 The extracted information will be [linked to a chemical index of FCCs, the references,](#)
422 [and a pre-coded overview of human health outcomes. It will be](#) presented graphically as
423 an interactive dashboard using PowerBI, including diagrams, heat maps, bar plots
424 and/or tables to visualize the main outcomes. The focus will be placed on the link
425 between human exposure to FCCs and associated health outcomes. Integrated filters
426 will allow the selection and highlighting of specific information, e.g., in relation to study
427 design, population types, chemical groups, and the publication year. For filtered data
428 sets, the underlying references will always be linked. A narrative summary in the form of
429 a peer-reviewed scientific manuscript will further explain the presented results and
430 provide background information.

431 The systematic evidence map linking FCCs to human health effects will provide a
432 comprehensive overview of the existing literature and will complement the systematic
433 evidence map on migrating and extractable FCCs (Geueke et al., 2023), the systematic
434 overview of the presence of FCCs in humans (Geueke, Parkinson, et al., 2024), and the
435 systematic evidence map of human health effects of plastic chemicals (Seewoo et al.,
436 2023). Together, these sources will provide a better understanding of the human health
437 [effectimpacts](#) of chemical exposure from FCMs, highlight knowledge gaps and identify
438 areas for further investigation.

439

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473 Data availability statement

474 The supplementary information that supports the findings of this study are openly
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488 **Abbreviations**

489 CHMS – Canadian Health Measures Survey

490 FCA – food contact article

491 FCC – food contact chemical

492 FCM – food contact material

493 HBM4EU – European Human Biomonitoring Initiative

494 ICD – International Classification of Diseases

495 KONEHS – Korean National Environmental Health Survey

496 NHANES – National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey

497 PECOS – population, exposure, comparator, outcome, study design

498 SAB – scientific advisory group

499 SCOD – Six Clusters of Disease

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